

Evaluating Railway Noise Sources Using Distributed Microphone Array and Graph Neural Networks

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Abstract: Identifying and evaluating railway noise sources is beneficial for establishing more targeted suppression and mitigation strategies. This paper proposes a novel approach to evaluate dominant railway noise sources for all bogie regions, by using an array of microphones and a physics-informed graph neural networks (GNN) model. The GNN model encodes not only the acoustic data collected by the microphone array but also the spatial relationship between noise sources and microphones, and it also considers the physical background of sound in terms of Doppler effect and acoustic attenuation. In-situ measurements of railway noises have been taken on an operating metro line to train and validate the GNN model which exhibits satisfactory performance in evaluating the noise sources of interest. The proposed approach enables a more flexible and cost-effective microphone array implementation strategy in comparison to the commonly adopted commercialized acoustic beamforming system.

Keywords: Railway noise source; Graph neural networks; Acoustic beamforming; Microphone array; Transportation noise

1. Introduction

To conduct noise evaluation, commonly used noise measurement instruments are diffuse-field, pressure-field, and free-field microphones (sound level meter). They are designed for indoor/in-car measurement considering the sound wave reflections, flush mounting withstanding rough handling and large pressure levels, and wide-field directional measurement with few influences of wave reflections, respectively. The regular microphones are tiny and light with good flexibility and have been applied for the evaluation of the railway noise according to standards with an appropriate arrangement (ISO, 2017, 2016). Despite its wide application in railway-related noise evaluation, this measurement method internally captures all the sound pressure at the installation point, which also leads to a high possibility of disturbance by unwanted noise sources. To reduce the disturbance, approaching the setup point to the concerned noise source could help to some extent, nevertheless,

it increases the installation difficulties and expenses in general cases, and may sometimes be impossible and even unsafe for the high-speed railway measurement that operates largely in the high elevated bridges. Further speaking, the railway system is a very complicated noise system, it contains the lower frequency structure-borne noise from bridges (Song et al., 2017), track plates, etc., and mid-to-high frequency rolling noise from wheel and rail, aerodynamic noise from pantograph region, motor noise, etc (Thompson, 2008). Identifying the main noise source components and figuring out its generation mechanism is essential for adopting effective noise suppression strategies. In this sense, the beamforming method, which localizes the noise sources by a specially designed microphone array and data processing techniques (Christensen and Hald, 2011; Johnson and Dudgeon, 1993), has been extensively applied to identify the locations and frequency components of noise sources for the high-speed railway (Gomes et al., 2015; Noh, 2017; Poisson et al., 2008; Talotte et al., 2003), wind-turbine (Buck et al., 2013; Kröber, 2014), aircraft (Sijtsma, 2012; Yu and Huang, 2018), etc. Although beamforming system has been proven to be effective in targeting the predominant noise source, since the most basic concept of the beamforming technique is to calculate time delay and sum (or phase shift in frequency domain) for each sound receiver at a set of predesigned array distance gaps, its spatial resolution is thus inevitably limited by the physical array size. Remembering that the spatial resolution is proportional to the distance between array and source (this distance cannot be much smaller than the beamforming array diameter) and inversely proportional to sound wavelength, thus only the higher frequency noise component could achieve a reasonable spatial resolution during a beamforming analysis. In other words, To maintain a decent spatial resolution in a larger targeting area, the size of the beamforming array also needs to be large enough, which is inevitably expensive and cumbersome, limiting its practical application. By contrast, a small-size beamforming array could only achieve a decent spatial resolution for some high-frequency noise components within a very limited targeting area (Gade et al., 2013), which indicates defects of the conventional beamforming system as inflexibility, high installation cost, high maintenance fee, etc. in railway noise source identification and evaluation. Hence, it would be

much more cost-efficient and favorable if a flexible and sparsely implemented array of microphones based on a large-size acoustic beamforming system as the upper bound might reach equally competent performance with much less budget required.

For the railway noise source evaluating task in this study, we are focusing on the noise sources around the bogie regions, which have been identified by the large-size acoustic beamforming system as several most noisy locations requiring more targeted noise suppression measures. Other potential noise source locations (pantograph region; bridge region; air conditioner region, etc.) are not thoroughly evaluated in this research. This task is essentially analogous to a specific branch of speech recognition which requires extraction of acoustic targets (voices from a videoed human, bogies` regional noise) of interest among noisy environments, especially for a railway system that consists of numerous noise sources and is operating in an open environment with relatively large source-microphone distances. Under this circumstance, machine learning (ML) methods, especially neural networks (NNs), can be powerful, and there have been a series of works on neural network-based speech recognition. As early as 1994, C. Che et. al. explored the possibility of integrating multi-layer perceptrons (MLP) with microphone arrays for more accurate speech recognition in variable acoustic environments (Che et al., 1994). With the rapid development of deep learning in recent years, convolutional neural networks (CNN) have been adopted in some of the works for either distant (Swietojanski et al., 2014) or multichannel recognition (Xiao et al., 2016). Other relevant studies focus on robust speech recognition or separation with the help of recurrent neural networks (RNN) or more specifically, long short-term memory framework (Hori et al., 2017; Meng et al., 2017; Perotin et al., 2018). These applications of ML methods greatly improve the recognition performance of microphone arrays by extracting features of interest in time and frequency domains and it is expected to be extended to a railway system scenario in which most applications of microphone arrays in railway systems are for the detection of faulty bearings (D. Zhang et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020a, 2017; S. Zhang et al., 2018) but limited literature can be found on localized railway noise identification or evaluation by using distributed microphone arrays

except for some relatively early investigations. Nevertheless, since the layout of microphone arrays is preferred to be flexible and sparse in railway systems subject to variable implementing situations, realizing ML-aided railway noise source evaluation requires generalization capability which the conventional CNN framework does not possess. In addition, the source-microphone spatial relationships are seldom encoded into the propagation process of neural networks but are rather treated separately, which motivates this study by introducing graph neural networks (GNN).

GNN is a novel and growing popular learning paradigm, which takes in not only measured data but also the topological structures of graphs. There has been pioneering work applying GNN to machinery fault diagnosis (Zhang et al., 2020b). GNNs are also used in many studies in social science, chemistry, and intelligent transportation systems to represent social networks (Wu et al., 2018), large molecules (Fout et al., 2017), and traffic networks (Zhao et al., 2019) where GNNs fully take advantage of the structured data by naturally encoding the spatial information in a graph. This inspires us when considering the case of characterizing/ localizing sources/ damages with a network/array of sensors, to abstract the entire layout into a graph. The authors conducted some pilot studies on monitoring residue torques of multiple bolted joints (Zhou et al., 2021a) and inference of multiple damages (Zhou et al., 2021b) by implementing a flexible network of piezoelectric sensing elements (under the principles of electromechanical impedance and ultrasonic guided waves respectively) and developing physics-informed GNN models. These pilot investigations in SHM sectors enlighten our thinking in applying GNN for railway noise source evaluation in an operating metro line, on which the moving train and the implemented microphones naturally form up a series of time-transforming graphs for learning and inference, which establishes the core philosophy of this paper.

This paper presents a physics-informed Graph Neural Network (GNN) model to characterize railway noise sources induced by passing trains for bogie regions. The graph is formulated by treating the implemented array of microphones and the moving railway noise sources as static and

dynamic vertices respectively, and the propagating acoustic waves between the sources and the microphones as edges. In this way, the running train and the microphones naturally generate a series of topologically homeomorphic graphs which can be unfolded along with the time series for learning under the GNN framework, which is the main contribution of this study. The propagation processes of railway noise from noise sources to microphones are encapsulated as virtual physics-informed messages that pass within the graph incorporating acoustic attenuation and Doppler effect. In this way, the knowledge of the user can be passed into the algorithm via the structure of the data (Tsialiamanis et al., 2021). A series of in-situ experiments were conducted using both an array of microphones and a commercialized acoustic beamforming system for railway noise evaluation on an operating metro line in the Chinese Mainland. The proposed GNN model is validated using the in-situ measurements, and results demonstrate that the proposed method enables railway noise source evaluation with microphones implemented under a more economical and flexible strategy while achieving equally satisfactory results in comparison to the beamforming device, which is powerful but expensive and cumbersome, which is the value of this study from a practical perspective.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 elaborates on the in-situ monitoring test conducted in an operating metro line using both the commercial acoustic beamforming system and the distributed microphone array; Section 3 introduces the concept of GNN and presents the development of the proposed GNN model abstracted from the in-situ monitoring scenario; Results and comparisons on the performance of the proposed approach are demonstrated in Section 4, and Section 5 draws the conclusions.

2. In-situ monitoring test

2.1. Experimental Setup

To capture dominant railway noise sources in practical scenarios, a series of in-situ experiments were conducted on a high-elevated operating metro line with two sets of individual measurement systems installed at neighboring spots, as shown in Figure 1.

The first measurement system consists of twelve free-field microphones (Type 4939, B&K Ltd.) which form a distributed array within one cross-section. To identify the wheelset position for source-microphone distance calculation and Doppler effect elimination in each time instance (details to be elaborated in Section 3), four 3-axis accelerometers (Series 3023, Dytran, Inc.) were installed on the rail web and rail foot of midspan and support for one rail section that is perpendicular to the array located cross-section. The collected rail vibration data was also applied to automatically locate the very moment of wheelset passing with a low-pass filter. Both the acoustic measurements and acceleration data were collected using a 16-Channel datalogger (SIRIUS DAQ, Dewesoft, d.o.o.) to ensure data synchronization, overall measurement setup for the first system is presented in Figure 1; The second measurement system is the moving source acoustic beamforming system, including a sliced pentagram array with 30 microphones (WA-1676-W-002, B&K Ltd.) and 24 channel datalogger (LAN-XI System, B&K Ltd.) and a dual-photocell detecting the position and velocity of the passing train, which can also be installed with the distributed array for train positioning. Figure 2 illustrates the implementation positions of the distributed microphones, the acoustic beamforming system, and the accelerometers, and Figure 3 shows the pictures of the test site and the implementation process.

All experiments were conducted with one metro train. The train contains eight bogies and four coaches, among which the traction coaches are the second and the third ones. To control the influencing factors, the train was operated during the skylight maintenance period, and the

operating velocity was controlled to be 20 km/h, 40 km/h, 60 km/h, 80 km/h, 100 km/h in each test round which covers three repetitive measurements under one speed.

Figure 1. In-situ test setup for noise measurement.

Figure 2. Implementation locations of the measurement systems.

Figure 3. Pictures of in-situ test with: (a) the distributed microphone array and accelerometers; and (b) the acoustic beamforming system.

2.2. Beamforming noise source identification

In this section, we followed the derivation of (Philip M. Morse and K. Uno Ingard, 1987; Zhang et al., 2019) to briefly introduce the key ideas of the acoustic beamforming analysis. The basic idea for conventional beamforming noise identification is the delay and sum strategy in time domain and phase shift in frequency domain. The beamforming response function is generated with an assumption that the noise sources to be identified are all described as uncorrelated monopoles, with a definition of a plane where the noise source is to be located and then mesh the plane with expected spatial resolution grids for source searching, then, the beamforming output in the time domain at the searched grid can be expressed as:

$$q_j(\tau) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M 4\pi r_{jm} \cdot p_m(r_m, t_j) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M 4\pi r_{jm} \cdot p_m(r_m, \tau + \frac{r_{jm}}{c_0}) \quad (1)$$

where the p_m is the measured sound pressure of the m^{th} microphone; r_{jm} represents the distance from the j^{th} vertex of the target source plane to the m^{th} microphone; r_m represents the distance between the monopole noise source to the m^{th} microphone; c_0 represents the sound traveling speed

in the air and the relationship between the sound emission time τ and receiving time t for the j^{th} vertex is

$$\tau = t - \frac{r_{jm}}{c_0} \quad (2)$$

Recall that the noise source is assumed to be an independent monopole given by

$$p(r_m, t) = \frac{q(\tau)}{4\pi r_m} = \frac{e^{i\omega(t - \frac{r_m}{c_0})}}{4\pi r_m} \quad (3)$$

The time delay is calculated by r_m/c_0 ; $q(\tau)$ is the source strength. Taking Eq. (3) into Eq. (1), the beamforming output at the j^{th} vertex can be generated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{q}_j(t) &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M 4\pi r_{jm} \cdot p_m\left(r_m, \tau + \frac{r_{jm}}{c_0}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{r_{jm}}{r_m} e^{i\omega\left(t - \frac{r_m}{c_0} + \frac{r_{jm}}{c_0}\right)} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $p_m(r_m, \tau + \frac{r_{jm}}{c_0})$ is the delayed microphone signals (based on the distance among microphones and j^{th} vertex). If the searched j^{th} vertex contains the noise source ($r_m = r_{jm}$), then the beamforming output (\tilde{q}) is to be equal to the theoretical monopole noise source, and the noise source is thus identified.

Critical steps for a conventional beamforming analysis are briefly described so far. Additional steps eliminating the influence of the Doppler effect and tracking the measurement noise source over a certain distance when conducting the beamforming analysis for the railway moving source identification are required. First of all, the sound pressure of a moving monopole recorded by the m^{th} microphone is given by

$$p_m(r_m, t) = \frac{q(\tau)}{4\pi r_m(\tau) \left| 1 - \frac{c_t}{c_0} \cos\theta(\tau) \right|^2} \quad (5)$$

The beamforming output for a moving source can be obtained easily by reversing Eq. (5) as

$$\tilde{q}_j(\tau) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M 4\pi |r_{jm}(\tau_j)| \cdot p_m(r_{jm}, t_j) \cdot \left| 1 - \frac{c_t}{c_0} \cos \theta(\tau_j) \right| \quad (6)$$

where the $r_{jm}(\tau_j)$ represents the distance between the j^{th} vertex moving with the train, which is a function of the emission time τ_j ; $\theta(\tau)$ is the angle between the moving direction and the source-array path, as presented in Figure 4; $p_m(r_{jm}, t_j)$ is the reconstructed receiving sound pressure signal according to the noise source emission time. The relationship between the noise emission time and receiving time holds the relation as

$$t_j = \tau_j + \frac{r_{jm}(\tau_j)}{c_0} \quad (7)$$

Due to the changing $r_{jm}(\tau)$, the signal receiving time sequence corresponding to the emission time is also changing, therefore the original measured sound pressure signal needs to be interpolated linearly to match the time sequences of the receiving signal with the emission source so that the moving source beamforming algorithm can be implemented. This kind of classic dedopplerization method resamples the received signal using the relationship between noise emission time and receiving time. Given the location of the concerned noise sources, they can be explicitly calculated simultaneously with the measurement signal. The reconstructed signal possesses a new time sequence keeping the same sampling frequency as the original receiving one, and the reconstructed sound pressure signal is interpolated linearly with a function of the train traveling speed. To be more straightaway, the reconstructed signal thus actually elongates the time sequence of original receiving signal to eliminate the increased frequency by the Doppler effect. Similarly, it shortens

the time sequence to increase the signal frequency when the noise source point passes the measurement plane. Figure 4 shows the exact procedures of doing the linear interpolation on the receiving signals for dedopplerization. Additionally, it should be noted that the vertex is moving with the noise source and the beamforming algorithm traces the vertex within the array open-angle.

Figure 4. Dedopplerization processing through the noise source emission time

Once the moving source beamforming analysis is done, the beamforming output $\tilde{q}_j(\tau)$ represents an estimate of the noise source at the j^{th} vertex within the meshed target plane (the moving railway train body in our circumstance), by using the Fourier transform on $\tilde{q}_j(\tau)$, the sound intensity of a monopole noise source can be estimated as

$$I = \frac{p_m^2(r_m, \omega)}{\rho c_0} = \frac{|\tilde{Q}_j(\omega)|^2}{16\pi^2 r_m^2 \rho c_0} \quad (8)$$

The sound power and sound intensity hold the relation as

$$P = 4\pi r_m^2 \cdot I \quad (9)$$

It should be still noted that beamforming noise identification is a kind of far-field noise identification technique, and all the output results are based on the assumption that the noise source consists of independent monopoles. Therefore, to get a more realistic sound power level of the noise

source when applied in the engineering practice, kinds of calibrated absolute source estimation strategies need further to be made based on the beamforming results (Christensen and Hald, 2011; Hald, 2005), which, however, is not the scope of this research. More extensive computational steps for different kinds of acoustic beamforming analyses can be found in (Brooks and Humphreys, 1999; Chiariotti et al., 2019; Pierce, 2019; Santana, 2017; Zhang et al., 2019). Additionally, **In this study, we use identification results obtained from the acoustic beamforming system as our ground truths to train the machine learning models proposed here for localized railway noise sources evaluation.**

2.3. In-situ measurements and bogie positioning

In this section, the measured sound pressure during a train passing at speed of 100 km/h from the cross-sectional array was presented in Figure 5 as an illustrative example for our measurement. The sampling frequency is 50 kHz. The truncated signal length is 10 s, which has shown to be enough for capturing the whole train passing period. The obtained transient sound pressure was then processed to generate the averaged sound pressure level (SPL) spectrum with a one-third octave frequency band range from 630 Hz to 10000 Hz (Figure 7(a)). The analyzed frequency range was determined by the sound source resolution of the beamforming array, where the lower frequency noise component has a much longer wavelength, which cannot be well identified with the dimension of our beamforming array. The SPL spectrum of the cross-sectional array shows that the dominant frequency band ranges from 630 Hz to 1250 Hz, and 2500 Hz to 3150 Hz.

Figure 6 presents the spatial noise source distribution results (sound intensity level, SIL) from the beamforming array with the sampling frequency of 32768 Hz. The dominant noise sources are located at the 8 vehicle bogies (four coaches with 8 bogies) and the pantograph area. The middle two coaches, which are the traction ones, have stronger noise sources than the head and trailing coaches without traction engines. To evaluate the railway noise sources, Figure 7(b) shows the spectrum and overall SWL of 8 bogie regions at 100 km/h corresponding to the beamforming

results presented in Figure 6. Two dominant frequency bands, which are 630 Hz to 1250 Hz for all bogies and 2000 Hz to 3150 Hz for the middle 6 bogies that are located near the traction engines, have been detected. The middle three bogies (fourth, fifth, and sixth) were evaluated to be the noisiest regions, which thus should be carefully treated by appropriate mitigation measures. Comparing the spectrums of distributed array (Figure 7(a)) and beamforming array (Figure 7(b)), it is found that beamforming array has well identified the noise sources both in spatial domain and frequency domain, both the noisiest regions and their exact noise frequency components are presented, while all microphones in the distributed array have a relatively consistent frequency characteristic, the only feature that possesses hidden noise source information is the value differences of SPL, which requires further processing with consideration of the spatial-temporal relationship of the noise source and noise component before being applied to source evaluation.

Figure 5. Sound pressure of distributed array at 100 km/h.

Figure 6. Spatial noise source distribution (SIL) at 100 km/h.

Figure 7. Spectrums at 100 km/h captured by: (a) the distributed microphone array (SPL); and (b) the acoustic beamforming system at 8 bogie regions (SWL).

To make good use of the underlying information hidden in the different SPL from the cross-sectional array, we further encoded the distance information in our proposed model. According to the spatial locations of microphones in the cross-sectional array and the installed rail accelerometer that is in parallel to the cross-sectional array, the source-receiver distance (bogies to microphones) can be calculated as

$$D_{bK} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{K,1} & d_{K,2} & d_{K,3} & d_{K,4} \\ d_{K,5} & d_{K,6} & d_{K,7} & d_{K,8} \\ d_{K,9} & d_{K,10} & d_{K,11} & d_{K,12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where D_{bK} represent the distance matrix from the K^{th} bogie to each microphone. The source-receiver distance can be calculated through the horizontal distance from

$$d_{K,j} = \sqrt{d_{hj}^2 + d_{vj}^2 + L_K^2} \quad (11)$$

where, according to Figure 2, d_{hj} and d_{vj} is the horizontal distance from the microphone M_j to the track center (7.5 m, 25 m and 40 m) and vertical distance to the track plane (1.2 m, 3.5 m, 5 m, 7.5 m). The calculation of the longitudinal distance L_K from the K^{th} bogie to the plane of the cross-sectional array is based on our installed rail accelerometers. A 20 Hz low-pass filtering (according to the wheelbase and train operating velocity) was conducted first to locate the wheelset passing instants (Figure 8). The passing moment of the first bogie center was then determined through an

average time instance of the first and the second wheelset passing instant (t_{w1} and t_{w2} , correspond to Figure 8), written as

$$t_{b1} = \frac{t_{w1} + t_{w2}}{2} \quad (12)$$

The longitudinal distance L_K can thus be calculated according to the train velocity c_t ,

$$L_i = (t_{b1} - t) \cdot c_t + L_{vehK} \quad (13)$$

where L_{vehK} represent the gap distance among bogies (central distance between the first and the second bogie $L_{bd1} = 15.7 \text{ m}$, central distance between the second and the third bogies $L_{bd2} = 7.1 \text{ m}$), which can be calculated as

$$L_{vehK} = L_{bd1} \times \left\lfloor \frac{K}{2} \right\rfloor + L_{bd2} \times \left\lceil \frac{K-1}{2} \right\rceil \quad (14)$$

Figure 8. Wheelset positioning (20 Hz low-pass filtered rail acceleration).

3. Establishment of physics-informed graph neural network model

The procedures of railway noise source identification by the moving source beamforming analysis with the specially-designed microphone array have been elaborated in the previous section. The dominant noise sources and noise components are explicitly presented. On the contrary, the

¹ The half bracket $\lfloor * \rfloor$ is to round of number toward negative infinity.

distributed microphone array which equally captured the coupled noise from the railway system, cannot achieve the same noise source evaluation as the beamforming array does. In this section, we added the GNN model considering the noise sources' spatial-temporal relationships to the distributed array measurement system, expecting to achieve a similar noise sources evaluation.

3.1. Introduction of message passing neural networks

Prior to the establishment of a specific GNN model for this case, it is necessary to describe the basic idea of graph and message passing neural networks.

Generally speaking, a graph \mathcal{G} can be noted as $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, E)$, where \mathcal{V} is the set of vertices, and E is the set of edges (Wu et al., 2020). A graph can be used to model entities and the relationship between them. For example, the roads in a transportation system are vertices and their intersections are edges (Zhao et al., 2019). The atoms in a molecule are vertices and their bonds are edges (Gilmer et al., 2017). The people in a social network are vertices and their interactions or connections are edges (Qiu et al., 2018).

In addition, each vertex $v \in \mathcal{V}$ may have a feature \mathbf{x}_v and a label \mathbf{y}_v . Each edge $(\mu, v) \in E$ may have a property $p_{\mu,v}$. Based on the graph structure and the vertex features, edge properties, and vertex labels, many operations can be conducted. Specifically, graph convolution (Kipf and Welling, 2016) can be conducted, which is inspired but different from conventional 2D convolution in CNNs. Figure 9 illustrates a standard 2D convolution in CNNs and an inspired simple graph convolution in GCNs respectively. The 2D convolution takes a weighted average of pixel values of the red pixel along with its neighbors, which are ordered and have a fixed size. Correspondingly, a simple graph convolution integrates the vertex features of the red vertex v and its neighbors $\mu \in N(v)$ to get a hidden representation. This integration can also be weighted according to the edge properties $p_{\mu,v}$. It can be noticed that a GCN can flexibly handle unordered entities and their relationship.

Figure 9. Two kinds of convolutions: (a) Grid convolution; (b) Graph convolution.

The vanilla GCN proposed by Kipf and Welling (Kipf and Welling, 2016) can be categorized as spectral-based GCN. Although this kind of GCN has its theoretical background in spectral graph theory, it works on a global scale and fails to handle the case that graph size is changing. In this study, we follow the concept of message passing neural network (Gilmer et al., 2017), which falls in another category called spatial-based GCN. Since the operations in this network are not restricted to graph convolution, in the rest of this paper, both the message passing neural network and the proposed GNN we proposed are called “GNN” rather than “GCN”.

At step i , in an undirected graph \mathcal{G} with vertex hidden state $\mathbf{s}_v^{(i)}$ and edge features $\mathbf{p}_{\mu,v}$, the forward propagation in message passing neural network has two phases, a message passing phase, and a readout phase. The message passing is defined in terms of message functions $\mathcal{M}^{(i)}$ and vertex update functions $\mathcal{U}^{(i)}$.

$$\mathbf{m}_v^{(i+1)} = \sum_{\mu \in N(v)} \mathcal{M}^{(i)}(\mathbf{s}_v^{(i)}, \mathbf{s}_\mu^{(i)}, \mathbf{p}_{\mu,v}) \quad (15)$$

where $N(v)$ denotes the neighbors of v and $\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(i)}$ denotes the state of vertex μ at this step.

During the message passing phase, the hidden state $\mathbf{s}_v^{(i)}$ of each vertex in the graph is updated based on messages $\mathbf{m}_v^{(i+1)}$ it receives:

$$\mathbf{s}_v^{(i+1)} = \mathcal{U}^{(i)}(\mathbf{s}_v^{(i)}, \mathbf{m}_v^{(i+1)}) \quad (16)$$

Finally, the readout phase computes a feature vector for the whole graph using some readout function \mathcal{R} according to

$$\hat{y} = \mathcal{R}(\{\mathbf{s}_v^{(l)} | v \in \mathcal{G}\}) \quad (17)$$

The message functions $\mathcal{M}^{(i)}$, vertex update functions $\mathcal{U}^{(i)}$ and readout function \mathcal{R} are all learned differentiable functions.

3.2. Graph formulation of microphone array and noise source

While machine learning algorithms, particularly neural networks (NNs) have been extensively adopted in different disciplines including acoustic recognition and noise identification or evaluation, the primary objective to be trained and recognized is basically restricted to individual signals captured from solitary sensors. The performance is satisfactory providing all valuable information is retained within each of the signals. When it comes to the scenario of a distributed microphone array, or in a more general term, a network of sensors, features extracted solely from the captured signals may not adequately cover all information of interest. The key issue lies in the fact that an array of microphones forms up a graph with a specific topological structure which can be highly useful for noise source evaluation. Dealing with this kind of structured data goes beyond the capability of conventional ML algorithms that primarily focus on learning input-output mappings in vector spaces. If one attempts to treat the entire array of microphones as a unity input for learning, normal ML algorithms require the permutation of input vector (i.e., placement of microphones) in the testing stage to be identical to that in the training stage, otherwise, they would fail upon any alteration of microphone positions. Therefore, a new learning framework is desired to capture relationships between objects from a more general perspective than vector spaces, which puts forward the introduction of GNNs.

Consider a train passing over a rail section bearing K moving sources of noise with M microphones randomly implemented in nearby regions, as shown in Figure 10(a). Any major noise signal captured by one microphone can be the superposition of acoustic waves generated from all potential sources, and a series of lines are created connecting the microphone with each of the

sources marking the relationship. Following this process, a bipartite graph is formulated with all microphones and sources serving as vertices of the graph, and all interconnecting lines serving as edges, as shown in Figure 10(b).

To interpret the process in graph language, microphones and sources are encoded into a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, E)$, where \mathcal{V} denotes the vertex set and E denotes the edge set. Specifically, there are two kinds of vertices. The source set \mathcal{V}_S contains source vertices while the microphone set \mathcal{V}_M contains microphone vertices. A bipartite graph is a graph whose vertices can be divided into two independent and disjoint sets \mathcal{V}_S and \mathcal{V}_M such that every edge connects an element in \mathcal{V}_S to an element in \mathcal{V}_M ; “complete” means each of the element in \mathcal{V}_S is connected to all elements in \mathcal{V}_M , and vice versa.

The relations between microphones and sources are encoded into edges. Each microphone will receive sounds from all sources. This logical relation can be expressed by a directed graph and the direction of edges follow the causality. Each source vertex is pointing to a microphone vertex. When μ is pointing to v , there exists an edge (μ, v) . The distance between μ and v is denoted as $d_{\mu,v}$.

Within the graph \mathcal{G} , vertices and edges are all substances with states or properties:

1. Each vertex v has an initial state denoted by $s_v^{(0)}$;
2. Each edge (μ, v) has two edge properties, one is the distance between them, denoted as $d_{\mu,v}$; another is the relative velocity between them, denoted as $c_{\mu,v}$.

Figure 10. From distributed microphone array to graph: (a) microphone array; (b) directed graph.

Initial State of vertex

Before describing the message passing, we need to define the initial state of each vertex. In simple terms, the initial state of the source vertex is the SWLs in different one-third octave frequency bands. The initial states of other vertices are set as zeros. For vertex $\mu \in \mathcal{V}_S$, its initial state $s_\mu^{(0)}$ is defined as:

$$s_\mu^{(0)} = \mathbf{x}_\mu \quad (18)$$

where \mathbf{x}_μ is a vector containing the SWLs in different one-third octave frequency bands; one example is presented in Figure 7(b).

It should be emphasized that, when beamforming is no longer available, the values of SWL are no longer provided, but to be inferred by the well-trained GNN, which should refer to Section 3.5 *Training GNN and Inferences of Noise Sources*.

For vertex $v \in \mathcal{V}_S$, its initial state $s_v^{(0)}$ is defined as:

$$s_v^{(0)} = 0 \quad (19)$$

Edge properties

Within a short period of time, for a source vertex $\mu \in \mathcal{V}_S$, a microphone $v \in \mathcal{V}_M$ and an edge (μ, v) , the following information at this moment is given.

- The distance between microphone vertex v and the train $d_{v,t}$;
- The physical distance between two vertices $d'_{\mu,v}$, which can refer to Figure 1 and Eq. (11);
- The velocity of train c_t which is negative when the source vertex has not crossed the distributed array and positive when the source vertex has crossed it.

Note that the velocity of sound traveling in the air is c_0 .

As shown in Figure 11 (upper-left), when the microphone vertex v receives information from the source vertex μ , the source vertex is not located where it sends this message. Therefore, the equivalent distance between μ and v of this edge in this graph $d_{\mu,v}$ should not directly take $d'_{\mu,v}$ but requires slight compensation, which is calculated as follows.

$$d'_\mu = \sqrt{d'_{\mu,v}{}^2 - d_{v,t}{}^2}$$

$$\Delta d = \frac{d'_{\mu,v}}{c} \times c_t \quad (20)$$

$$d_\mu = d'_\mu - \Delta d$$

$$d_{\mu,v} = \sqrt{d_\mu{}^2 + d_{v,t}{}^2}$$

Note that when c_t is negative, $-\Delta d$ is positive. the relationship between each vertex pair in the graph is constant.

Given the right edge property $d_{\mu,v}$, the relative velocity $c_{\mu,v}$ can be calculated as follows.

$$c_{\mu,v} = c_t \cos \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{d_{v,t}}{d_{\mu,v}}\right) \quad (21)$$

Correspondingly, $c_{\mu,v}$ is negative when the source is moving towards the microphone and positive when the source is moving away from the microphone, as shown in Figure 11 (upper-left) and Figure 11 (upper-right), respectively.

In this way, we can know two edge properties of edge (μ, v) , the distance $d_{v,t}$ and the relative velocity $c_{\mu,v}$.

Figure 11. Distance compensation.

Label of vertices

For each vertex v , its label is defined as:

$$l_v = \begin{cases} y_v & \text{if } v \in \mathcal{V}_M \\ 0 & \text{if } v \in \mathcal{V}_S \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where y_v is a vector containing the SPLs in different one-third octave frequency bands received by the microphone.

The nomenclature is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Nomenclature

Notations	Meaning
\mathcal{G}	Graph
\mathcal{V}	Vertex set
E	Edge set
\mathcal{V}_S	Noise source vertex set
\mathcal{V}_M	Microphone vertex set
$\mathcal{V}_{M(i)}$	The i^{th} microphone vertex subset $\mathcal{V}_{M(i)} \in \mathcal{V}_M (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$
v	A vertex in \mathcal{V} (\mathcal{V}_M or \mathcal{V}_S)
μ	A vertex in \mathcal{V}_S
(μ, v)	Edge from μ to v
$d_{\mu,v}$	The distance between μ and v
β	Learnable parameters describing the attenuation of each frequency interval
c_0	The velocity of sound
c_t	The velocity of train
$c_{\mu,v}$	The relative velocity between μ and v
$\mathbf{p}_{\mu,v}$	The edge property considering the attenuation
$\mathbf{P}_{\mu,v}$	The edge property considering the Doppler effect
\mathbf{x}_μ	The feature vector of source vertex $\mu \in \mathcal{V}_S$ (SWLs)
\mathbf{y}_v	The feature vector of microphone vertex $v \in \mathcal{V}_M$ (SPLs)
n	The number of time frames
M	The number of microphones
K	The number of bogie sources
$s_v^{(0)}$	The initial state of vertex v
l_v	The label of vertex v
$m_v^{(1)}$	The message received by vertex v during the 1 st message passing
$s_v^{(1)}$	The first state of vertex v
\hat{l}_v	The readout of vertex v

3.3. Message passing in the directed graph

Doppler effect & Acoustic attenuation

First of all, the doppler effect should be taken into account, which means the change in frequency of a wave in relation to an observer who is moving relative to the wave source.

$$f' = \frac{c}{c + c_{\mu,v}} f \quad (23)$$

where f' is the observed frequency, f is the emitted frequency; c is the propagation velocity of sound waves in the air; $c_{\mu,v}$ is the velocity of source relative to the microphone.

As illustrated in Figure 12, when blueshift occurs, the updated pressure level $x'_i = \alpha_{i-1}x_{i-1} + \alpha_i x_i$ except $x'_1 = \alpha_1 x_1 = x_1$. Similarly, when redshift occurs, the updated pressure level $x'_i = \alpha_i x_i + \alpha_{i+1} x_{i+1}$ except $x'_{13} = \alpha_{13} x_{13} = x_{13}$.

Figure 12. Illustration of blue shift and red shift.

For a specific edge (μ, v) , when $c_{\mu,v}$ is negative, the doppler effect matrix $P_{\mu,v}$ can be obtained as follows:

$$P_{\mu,v,i,i} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = 1 \\ \alpha_i & \text{if } i \geq 2 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

$$P_{\mu,v,i,i-1} = \alpha_{i-1} \text{ if } i \geq 2$$

For a specific edge (μ, ν) , when $c_{\mu,\nu}$ is positive, the doppler effect matrix $P_{\mu,\nu}$ can be calculated as follows:

$$P_{\mu,\nu,i,i} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = m \\ \alpha_i & \text{if } i \leq m - 1 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

$$P_{\mu,\nu,i,i+1} = \alpha_{i+1} \text{ if } i \leq m - 1$$

Following the above procedures, two examples are provided in Figure 13. When the relative velocity $c_{\mu,\nu}$ is -11.1 m/s (approaching the microphone) and the sound velocity is 343 m/s, a doppler effect matrix $P_{\mu,\nu}$ can be calculated, as shown in Figure 13(a). When the relative velocity is 16.7 m/s (leaving the microphone), the doppler effect matrix $P_{\mu,\nu}$ is shown in Figure 13(b).

Figure 13. Demonstration of Doppler effect matrix.

In terms of acoustic attenuation, it is natural to take the form of e^{-d} since sound waves decay exponentially concerning the propagation distance d . Considering that high-frequency waves attenuate faster while low-frequency waves attenuate slower, a learnable vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, sharing the same dimension as \boldsymbol{x} , is introduced in front of the distance. Correspondingly, for each edge (μ, ν) , the edge property is defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{p}_{\mu,\nu} = e^{-\boldsymbol{\beta}d_{\mu,\nu}} \quad (26)$$

where the i^{th} element β_i is a learnable parameter that summarizes the effect of distance for SWL x_i for frequency f_i .

Message passing

Based on this graph, a GNN can be formulated. This network falls into the framework of message passing neural networks (Gilmer et al., 2017). During the forward propagation, the output of each vertex is obtained in three steps.

In step 1, each vertex integrates the message from those vertices pointing to it, considering both the Doppler effect and wave attenuation.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{m}_v^{(1)} &= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathcal{M}^{(0)}(\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(0)}, d_{\mu,v}, c_{\mu,v}) \\ &= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathbf{p}_{\mu,v} \cdot \mathbf{P}_{c_{\mu,v}} \mathbf{s}_v^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

In step 2 (vertex updating), each vertex updates its state based on the message it received

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}_v^{(1)} &= \mathcal{U}^{(1)}(\mathbf{m}_v^{(1)}, \mathbf{s}_v^{(0)}) \\ &= \mathbf{W}^{(1)} \mathbf{m}_v^{(1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(1)} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

In step 3 (readout), each vertex updates its state based on the message it received

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{l}_v &= \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{s}_v^{(1)}) \\ &= \mathbf{W} \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{s}_v^{(1)}) + \mathbf{b} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where ReLU (rectified linear unit) is a type of activation function that induces non-linearity. Mathematically, ReLU elementwise conducts $y = \max(0, x)$.

Since no edges are pointing from microphone vertex to source vertices, the message passing in this graph basically simulates the process of noise sources shifting, propagating, and integrating. Specifically, $D_{c_{\mu,v}} \mathbf{s}_v^{(0)}$ calculates the updated initial state considering the Doppler effect between μ and v ; \cdot is elementwise product; $\mathbf{p}_{\mu,v} \cdot D_{c_{\mu,v}} \mathbf{s}_v^{(0)}$ considers the attenuation between μ and v . However, due to unknown contributing and interference factors as mentioned in the introduction, the received

information of each microphone is not directly the sum of contribution of each noise source. Therefore, the vertex updating and readout functions help to transform the received message to the predicted output \hat{l}_v , which is expected to be equal to the ground truth l_v .

Figure 14 illustrates the message passing in a small-scale case.

Figure 14. Message passing in the proposed model.

3.4. Extension to large graph

As mentioned in Section 3.2, at a specific short time period, we consider that the relationship between noise and microphone fixed and formulate a graph. However, the train is moving at a constant velocity c_t , as shown in Figure 15. It is assumed that each noise source remains the same during the whole period but what the microphones receive is changing. In this case, the vertex set \mathcal{V} and the edge set E remain the same, and the initial state of each vertex $s_v^{(0)}$ are also the same but the desired state of each microphone vertex o_v ($v \in \mathcal{V}_M$) is different. For each edge (μ, v) , the edge properties $d_{\mu,v}$ $c_{\mu,v}$ are changing. Therefore, for one case where the train is moving at a constant velocity c_t , and each noise source remains the same, we can formulate a large graph like Figure 16.

The source vertex set \mathcal{V}_S remains the same, while each moment (short time period) has one microphone set $\mathcal{V}_{M(i)}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) where n is the number of time slices. In essence, we are cutting the whole process into slices and then unfolding them into a large graph.

To summarize, in one run, we can obtain one large graph using the procedure in Table 2. If there are K bogie sources, M microphones, and n time frames, the number of vertices of this graph is $K + nM$.

Table 2. Procedures to formulate a graph.

<p>Represent each bogie source by a vertex μ</p> <p>Calculate the SWL x_μ of each source vertex $\mu \in \mathcal{V}_S$ using beamforming</p> <p>Initialize $s_\mu^{(0)} = x_\mu$</p> <p>Label $l_\mu = 0$</p> <p>For each time frame $[t_i - \frac{\Delta t}{2}, t_i + \frac{\Delta t}{2}]$</p> <p> For each microphone</p> <p> Create a microphone vertex v representing the microphone in this time interval</p> <p> Initialize $s_v^{(0)} = x_v$</p> <p> Obtain the microphone frequency signal in this time interval y_v</p> <p> Label $l_v = y_v$</p> <p> Create an edge (μ, v) from μ to v</p> <p> Obtain the distance between v and each source vertex $\mu \in N(v)$</p> <p> Obtain the nominal distance between v and μ based on Eq. (20) and attach it to edge (μ, v)</p> <p> Obtain the relative velocity between v and μ based on Eq. (21) and attach it to edge (μ, v)</p>
--

It should be noted that all these operations are on vertex level. Therefore, the number of microphones and the number of noise sources can be flexible. Given a graph, we looked at the

vertices we are interested in, first conducting message passing following Eq. (27) and then conducting vertex updating and readout, following Eq. (28) and Eq. (29).

Figure 15. Graph homeomorphic transformation.

Figure 16. Graph unfolding.

3.5. Training GNN and Inference of Noise Sources

It is expected that the output of a vertex (Eq. (29)) is equal to the label of vertices (Eq. (22)). Specifically, we are only interested in the final state of microphone vertex $v \in \mathcal{V}_M$. Given a training vertex set $\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_M$, the cost function is defined as:

$$J_{M_{tr}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}|} \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}} \|\hat{\mathbf{l}}_v - \mathbf{l}_v\|^2 \quad (30)$$

where $|\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}|$ is the number of vertices in $\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}$

For each $v \in \mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}$, the label \mathbf{l}_v is always known but the final state $\hat{\mathbf{l}}_v$ depends on the initial states of source vertices pointing to it $\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(0)}$ ($\mu \in N(v)$), the learnable vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ representing the attenuation effect, the weight matrices $\mathbf{W}^{(1)}$, \mathbf{W} and the bias vectors $\mathbf{b}^{(1)}$, \mathbf{b} . During the training, the $\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(0)}$ ($\mu \in N(v)$) is known and fixed. Thus, the training is done by minimizing the cost in the training vertex set $\min_{\Delta, \mathbf{W}^{(1)}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}^{(1)}, \mathbf{b}} J_{M_{tr}}$.

These parameters are encoded in the proposed GNN. It should be emphasized that this model works on the vertex level. When this model is well-trained, it implicitly describes the process of noise sources integrating into the sounds a microphone receives.

For an inference vertex set $\mathcal{V}_{M_{in}} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_M$, the cost function is defined as:

$$J_{M_{in}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{V}_{M_{in}}|} \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}_{M_{in}}} \|\hat{\mathbf{l}}_v - \mathbf{l}_v\|^2 \quad (31)$$

During the inference, we have already approximated the process of noise propagation by the proposed GNN, and all $\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{W}^{(1)}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}^{(1)}, \mathbf{b}$ have been known. By contrast, the initial states, $\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(0)}$ ($\mu \in N(v)$), representing the SWLs x_μ ($\mu \in N(v)$) are unknown. Therefore, the inference is conducted by minimizing the cost in the inference vertex set $\min_{x_\mu (\mu \in N(v))} J_{M_{in}}$. This inference follows the idea from (Bora et al., 2017), where a generative model is first constructed and trained to

capture how the observed measurements are generated, then used to infer the sources that generate the observed measurements.

The whole flowchart of training and utilizing the proposed GNN is summarized in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Flowchart of training proposed GNN and inference with the model.

As mentioned in Section 2.1, only one train was operated in the skylight maintenance period, and the operating velocity was controlled as 20 km/h, 40 km/h, 60 km/h, 80 km/h, 100 km/h with **repetitive** runs.

Each run was cut into n time steps and the time interval Δt is 0.1s. Since the sampling frequency of the microphone is 50 kHz, the frequency bin is thus 10 Hz, which is adequate for the concerned frequency range.

Each running speed is considered a case. For each case, we selected three runs and generate 3 graphs for this case, following the procedures presented in Table 2. Each graph represents the information collected from one run. For example, when the trained speed is 20 km/h, the length of one recording is 20s and there are 399 time frames. Since there are 8 bogies and 12 microphones, the total vertices of the first graph are $4796 = 8 + 12 \times 399$.

For each case, two graphs were used to train the proposed GNN. Each graph contains nM microphone vertices, corresponding to Figure 16. After training, the remaining one graph was used to evaluate the proposed GNN. Table 3 summarises the graphs for training and evaluating the proposed GNN. It should be emphasized that higher train speed would exhibit different patterns of noise generation. Therefore, for 5 cases, we trained 5 GNNs rather than using one to handle all.

Table 3. Data for training GNN and inference.

Case	Graph	Number of runs	Train speed (c_t)	Time	Window (Δt)	Slicing	Number of Frames (n)	Number of vertices	$ \mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}} $	$ \mathcal{V}_{M_{in}} $
1	1-3	3	20 km/h	20s	0.1s	0.05s	399	4796×3	4788×2	4788×1
2	4-6	3	40 km/h	20s	0.1s	0.05s	399	4796×3	4788×2	4788×1
3	7-9	3	60 km/h	10s	0.1s	0.05s	199	2396×3	2388×2	2388×1
4	10-12	3	80 km/h	10s	0.1s	0.05s	199	2396×3	2388×2	2388×1
5	13-15	3	100 km/h	10s	0.1s	0.05s	199	2396×3	2388×2	2388×1

All data were normalized to be within the same scale and prevent numerical problems during training and inference. First, all the distances are divided by the maximum distance. In addition, both the SWLs and the SPLs are min-max standardized.

The GNNs were initialized by Xavier (Kumar, 2017). The training was conducted by mini-batch gradient descent. Each minibatch contains 16 vertices in $\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}$. The training was conducted by Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2014) by 200 epochs. (Kingma and Ba, 2014)

In the inference stage, the SWLs to be inferred were randomly initialized between 0 to 1. The inference was conducted by Adam optimizer by 50 epochs.

Model training and noise source inference were conducted on a workstation with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7700HQ 2.8GHz processor, 12GB RAM, and an Nvidia GTX2070 Graphic Card.

3.6. Baseline models for comparison

To prove the superiority of our approach, three baseline models are developed.

Baseline 1 does not consider the Doppler effect. Specifically, different from the message passing in Eq. (24), the information of $c_{\mu, \nu}$ is not leveraged.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{m}_v^{(1)} &= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathcal{M}^{(0)}(\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(0)}, d_{\mu,v}) \\
&= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathbf{p}_{\mu,v} \cdot \mathbf{s}_v^{(0)}
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Baseline 2 does not involve the attenuation effect. Specifically, different from the message passing in Eq. (27), the information of $d_{\mu,v}$ is not leveraged.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{m}_v^{(1)} &= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathcal{M}^{(0)}(\mathbf{s}_\mu^{(0)}, c_{\mu,v}) \\
&= \sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \mathbf{P}_{c_{\mu,v}} \mathbf{s}_v^{(0)}
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

In Baseline 3, we directly trained a CNN to predict the SWL of a noise source x_μ based on the SPL of microphones y_v . Therefore, the input to the CNN is a 15-by-12 feature matrix, where 12 is the number of microphones. Out of 15 elements of the feature of one microphone, 13 elements are the SWLs of each frequency interval, 1 element is the distance between the microphone and the source of interest and the final 1 element is the relative velocity between them. The architecture of this CNN is summarized as follows.

Table 4 Architecture of CNN.

Layer	Operations in Layer	Conv filters	Size of output representation
Input			$[1 \times 15 \times 12]$
1	Convolution→ReLU	32 15×1 filter	$[32 \times 1 \times 12]$
2	Convolution→ReLU	13 1×1 filter	$[13 \times 1 \times 12]$
3	Flatten→Fully connected		64
4	Fully connected		13

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Noise evaluation results of GNN and distributed array

As mentioned in Section 2, for each round of tests under one speed level, there were three repetitive runs. Two runs were used for training GNN and one was used for testing GNN.

Figure 18 illustrates the inferred SWL of 8 bogies, compared with the results from the beamforming system when the train was running at 20 km/h. Figure 18(a) shows the ground truth from beamforming while Figure 18(b) shows the result inferred by GNN. The relative error is shown in Figure 18(c). It can be noticed that the inferred SWLs of all bogies are close to the ground truths. The accuracy of inference is measured by mean absolute error (MAE) and is 0.69 dB(A). For comparison, the standard absolute deviation of each frequency interval is between 0.78 dB(A) to 2.14 dB(A). Therefore, this MAE is quite acceptable. Figure 19 to Figure 22 illustrates the inference results of the other four cases. The MAEs are 0.54 dB(A), 0.56 dB(A), 0.73 dB(A) and 0.61 dB(A), respectively. Correspondingly, the average absolute deviation is around 1~4 for different one-third octave frequency bands.

Figure 18 to Figure 22 also show the capability of the GNN model and distributed array in evaluating the spectrum characteristics, though relatively larger inference errors can be found for non-predominant bogie regions and non-predominant frequency bands.

The noise source evaluation results generated by GNN and distributed array as well as the acoustic beamforming system at 100 km/h and 40 km/h are summarized in Table 5. For Case 5 (100 km/h), the GNN model and distributed array can effectively identify the noisiest sound frequencies and the noisiest bogie regions, with a maximum inference error of 1.69 dB(A)@4000 Hz at the first bogie region. The overall SWL inference error is even more trivial, with a maximum inference error of 0.49 dB(A) at the sixth bogie region. As for the 40 km/h (case 2), the GNN model and distributed array can also precisely rank the noisiest bogie regions, with the maximum inference error of the overall SWL as 0.42 dB(A) at the second bogie region. The noisiest frequency is imperfectly evaluated for the first bogie region and the eighth bogie region, and this inaccurate evaluation can be attributed to the existence of dual peaks in the spectrum (referring to Figure 19). The maximum inference error is 2.01 dB(A)@3150 Hz at the eighth bogie region. In all, the proposed GNN model and the distributed array can effectively evaluate the overall SWL for all bogie regions as the

traditionally large-size beamforming acoustic system does, with a full capability of determining the noisiest regions for target noise suppression. Therefore, the GNN model and distributed array have been demonstrated to be capable of surrogating the large-size acoustic beamforming system in railway noise source evaluation.

To further prove the superiority of our approach, the results using other baseline methods are shown in Figure 23. Without considering the Doppler effect, Baseline 1 performs slightly worse than the proposed GNN while Baseline 2 performs significantly worse than the proposed GNN without considering the attenuation effect. Although Baseline 3 takes the distance as a feature in the CNN model, it gives errors comparable to Baseline 2, which is not satisfactory. The reasons will be discussed in Section 4.2 and Section 4.3.

For the proposed model, each epoch takes around 7.6 seconds to traverse the microphone vertex set ($|\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}| = 4788 \times 2$). Therefore, the 200 epochs of training take around 25 minutes and 20 seconds. Regarding the inference, each epoch takes around 3.6 seconds to transverse the microphone vertex set ($|\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}| = 4788 \times 1$). Therefore, the 50 epochs of inference take around 12 minutes.

Both Baseline 1 and Baseline 2 shares a similar efficiency of training and inferences.

When it comes to Baseline 3, each epoch takes around 0.72s to transverse all combinations ($399 \times 8 \times 2$). Therefore, the 200 epochs of training take around 2 minutes and 25 seconds. The prediction based on the model, requiring no gradient descent, can be completed almost in an instant.

Figure 18. Inference for Case 1: (a) ground truth; (b) inference results; (c) inference error.

Figure 19. Inference for Case 2: (a) ground truth; (b) inference results; (c) inference error.

Figure 20. Inference for Case 3: (a) ground truth; (b) inference results; (c) inference error.

Figure 21. Inference for Case 4: (a) ground truth; (b) inference results; (c) inference error.

Figure 22. Inference for Case 5: (a) ground truth; (b) inference results; (c) inference error.

Table 5 Noise evaluation comparisons (SWL) at 100 km/h and 40 km/h

Region	Beamforming			GNN and Distributed array			Error	
	Peak dB(A)	Overall dB(A)	Rank	Peak dB(A)	Overall dB(A)	Rank	Max dB(A)	Overall dB(A)
100 km/h								
Bogie 1	100.2@ 1250 Hz	105.6	8 th	101.0@ 1250 Hz	105.8	8 th	1.69@ 5000 Hz	0.21
Bogie 2	102.6@ 1250 Hz	108.6	6 th	102.9@ 1250 Hz	108.6	6 th	1.26@ 5000 Hz	0.05
Bogie 3	103.3@ 3150 Hz	109.1	5 th	101.9@ 3150 Hz	108.7	5 th	1.37@ 3150 Hz	0.41
Bogie 4	104.8@ 1250 Hz	110.3	1 st	104.2@ 1250 Hz	110.1	1 st	1.48@ 3150 Hz	0.28
Bogie 5	105.3@ 800 Hz	110.3	1 st	103.9@ 800 Hz	109.9	2 nd	1.54@ 800 Hz	0.38
Bogie 6	104.9@ 800 Hz	110.3	1 st	103.6@ 800 Hz	109.8	3 rd	1.38@ 800 Hz	0.49
Bogie 7	104.8@ 1250 Hz	109.2	4 th	104.3@ 1250 Hz	108.8	4 th	1.29@ 800 Hz	0.38
Bogie 8	100.2@ 800 Hz	107.4	7 th	102.2@ 1250 Hz	107.4	7 th	1.58@ 3150 Hz	0.04
40 km/h								
Bogie 1	89.7@ 1000 Hz	95.7	7 th	89.4@ 1250 Hz	96.0	7 th	1.91@ 5000 Hz	0.28
Bogie 2	93.0@ 1250 Hz	98.3	2 nd	93.6@ 1250 Hz	98.8	2 nd	1.27@ 5000 Hz	0.42
Bogie 3	92.5@ 1250 Hz	97.8	4 th	93.1@ 1250 Hz	98.2	3 rd	1.32@ 3150 Hz	0.39
Bogie 4	94.1@ 2500 Hz	99.3	1 st	94.4@ 2500 Hz	99.6	1 st	1.35@ 3150 Hz	0.36
Bogie 5	92.2@ 1250 Hz	97.9	3 rd	92.6@ 1250 Hz	98.2	3 rd	1.03@ 800 Hz	0.24
Bogie 6	90.8@ 2500 Hz	96.8	6 th	91.0@ 2500 Hz	97.0	6 th	1.08@ 800 Hz	0.13
Bogie 7	92.4@ 1250 Hz	97.5	5 th	92.3@ 1250 Hz	97.6	5 th	1.39@ 800 Hz	0.04
Bogie 8	89.2@ 1000 Hz	94.2	8 th	87.5@ 2500 Hz	93.8	8 th	2.01@ 3150 Hz	0.41

Figure 23. Comparison between proposed GNN and 3 baseline models.

4.2. Comparison with Baseline 1 and Baseline 2

Proposed GNN VS Baseline 1

As mentioned in Section 4.1, Baseline 1 performs slightly worse than the proposed GNN, which should be due to the ignorance of the Doppler effect. However, this ignorance does not matter too much for the following reasons. The train will first approach the microphone array, where blue shifting occurred and the high-frequency SWL will be overestimated. By contrast, when the train is leaving the microphone, the high-frequency SWL is underestimated. As mentioned in Section 3.5, the inference was conducted based on the large graph constructed in one run. Therefore, the influence of blue shifting and red shifting will cancel out each other.

To further illustrate the importance of considering the Doppler effect, the following investigation was conducted. The training set $\mathcal{V}_{M_{tr}}$ and inference set $\mathcal{V}_{M_{in}}$ were both divided into two parts: the approaching part and leaving part. The former means that the middle of the train has not crossed the microphone array (referring to Figure 1) and the latter means that the middle of the train has crossed the microphone array. The proposed GNN was trained by one part (approaching or leaving) and then the inference of SWL was based on another part (leaving and approaching). The results are shown as follows.

Figure 25 presents the results in Case 2 when the train was 40 km/h. In (a), the proposed GNN was trained when the train was leaving but the inference was conducted based on data collected when the train was coming. As a result, the high-frequency SWL was overestimated while the low-frequency SWL was underestimated. The trend can be observed in Figure 24(a). By contrast, when the proposed GNN was trained when the train was approaching but the inference was conducted based on data collected when the train was leaving, the low-frequency SWL will be overestimated but the high-frequency SWL will be underestimated, as shown in Figure 24(b). This effect is more significant when the train was running at 100 km/h, as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 24. Inference error in Case 2: (a) GNN trained on leaving and used for approaching; (b) GNN trained on approaching and used for leaving.

Figure 25. Inference error in Case 5: (a) GNN trained on leaving and used for approaching; (b) GNN trained on approaching and used for leaving.

Proposed GNN VS Baseline 2

As mentioned in Section 3.3, high-frequency waves attenuate faster and low-frequency waves attenuate slower. To take this into account, we allow different attenuation ratios for different frequency levels and that's why β is a vector rather than a scalar. as shown in Eq. (26). We open up the proposed GNN training in Case 2 for example. The learned β is presented in Figure 26 and an obvious trend can be observed. The β_2 for 800 Hz is 1.45. The β_7 for 2500 Hz is 3.44. The β_{12} for 8000 Hz is 8.35. Figure 27 and 28 demonstrates how this factor influences the message passing in the graph to a microphone vertex.

Figure 27(a) demonstrates the case when the train has just passed this microphone. As shown in Figure 27(b) (c) and (d), the closer the distance, the larger the contribution. For example, the

distance between Bogie 8 and this microphone is 46.3m and the normalized distance is 0.235 (46.3/207). Therefore, the attenuation effect of this edge at this frequency is $p_{\mu,v} = e^{-1.45 \times 0.235} = 0.711$. In addition, the higher the frequency, the smaller the contribution. At 800 Hz, 71.1% can be propagated but at 8000 Hz, only 14.1% can be propagated. This phenomenon is more obvious when the train is farther away. In Figure 28, when the bogie was 180 m away from the microphone. The factor for 800 Hz is 26.5% while all the 8000 Hz information will be lost during the propagation.

It can be seen that this is an important element to be concerned about. However, as mentioned in Section 3.6, Baseline 2 directly skips this step and brutally adds up all the information from each bogie. The weights are illustrated in Figure 27(e) and Figure 28(e). The consequence is shown in Figure 29. It can be noticed that all the lines are stacked together. In addition, compared to Figure 18, the value is basically the average of all bogies, which means that Baseline 2 can still be used to infer the SWL in different one-third octave frequency bands. However, Baseline 2 fails to distinguish the SWLs contributed by different bogies because they indiscriminately contribute to what a microphone can receive. Basically, Baseline 2 averages the result of 8 bogies and considers it the truth for all of them.

A similar phenomenon can be found in Figure 30, demonstrating the inference results by Baseline 2 for Case 5.

As a result, the error increases to 2~4 times the error of the proposed GNN, as shown in Figure 24. This highlights the importance of attenuation effects.

Figure 26. Learned β in Case 2.

Figure 27. Illustration of one microphone vertex and 8 bogie vertices when the train is passing the microphone: (a) distance between vertices; (b) edge property at 800 Hz; (c) at 2500 Hz; (d) at 8000 Hz; (e) edge property in Baseline 2.

Figure 28. Illustration of one microphone vertex and 8 bogie vertices when the train is leaving the microphone: (a) distance between vertices; (b) edge property at 800 Hz; (c) at 2500 Hz; (d) at 8000 Hz; (e) edge property in Baseline 2.

Figure 29. Case 2 by Baseline 2: (a) Inference results; (b) inference errors.

Figure 30. Case 5 by Baseline 2: (a) Inference results; (b) inference errors.

4.3. Compared with Baseline 3 and tolerance to microphone reduction

As mentioned in Section 3.6, for the noise source of interest, its distance and relative velocities to 12 microphones are combined with what the microphone received, as the input features to the Baseline 3. This scheme is relatively straightforward.

The performances of Baseline 3 for Case 2 (40 km/h) and Case 5 (100 km/h) are shown in Figures 31 and 32, respectively. It can be noticed that the SWL results for 8 bogies are barely distinguishable. This phenomenon is quite similar to what happened in Figures 29 and 30 and should be ascribed to the crude handling of the attenuation effect. During the training, the distances between a bogie and the microphones are taken as features and, entangled with SPL values, directly input to the CNN. Thus, the CNN should learn by itself to simultaneously eliminate the Doppler effect and attenuation effect and to separate the different contributions from 8 bogies, which is very

difficult. In comparison, the propagation processes of railway noise can be parametrically encoded, as shown in Section 3.3, rather than be learned from scratch. This ability to naturally encode the relationship between objects is the essential advantage of GNN compared with CNN.

Another drawback of Baseline 3 is its intolerance of microphone reduction. As shown in Table 4, the input to Baseline3 is a 12-by-15 matrix. If one or several microphones are not included, Baseline 3 is not applicable. Actually, the motivation of this study is to represent the microphone array by a graph that allows the increase or decrease of vertices, as mentioned in Introduction and Section 3.2.

In comparison, as emphasized in Section 3.3, the proposed GNN, is operated on vertex level. Both training and inference can be conducted with any microphone vertex in the formulated graph. As a result, the proposed GNN exhibits the tolerance of sensor absence.

To prove this advantage, we removed M9, M5, and M1 in succession (referring to Figure 2). In this way, there are only 11, 10, and 9 microphones. In the 9-microphone setting, the graph has at least 1791 (9*199) microphone vertices and is still adequate to infer the SWLs of 8 bogies. As shown in Figure 33, the MAE does not dramatically increase when the number of microphones decreases. For example, even in the most dramatically changing case (Case 5 with 100 km/h), the MAE only increases from 0.61 to 0.76 when three microphones are removed. In essence, this tolerance should be ascribed to the graph formulation.

Figure 31. Case 2 by Baseline 3: (a) Inference results; (b) inference errors.

Figure 32. Case 5 by Baseline 3: (a) Inference results; (b) inference errors.

Figure 33. Influence of the number of microphones to inference errors.

4.4. Investigation of settings

Both the quality of data input to the proposed GNN and its architecture will influence its performance. Therefore, to make this study complete, we further investigated the influence of two factors: the time interval Δt and the size of hidden layer. The results are shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35, respectively.

As mentioned in Section 3.5, the time interval Δt of this study is selected as 0.1s. This is to ensure that the graph is relatively static in this short period so that we can unfold the slices on the time axis and make them a subset of the graph. The frequency bin is 10 Hz, which is also adequate.

By contrast, when the time interval is set as 1s, the train had passed a long distance and the SWL was calculated based on the average within this second. As a result, the spatial resolution is not adequate. The faster the train runs, the longer the distance one microphone vertex includes, and thus the smaller spatial resolution. As a result, the inference error was significantly larger. As shown in Figure 34, this effect is less significant when the time interval is set as 0.25 s.

In addition, we also determine the size of hidden layer of NN, which determines the size of $\mathbf{W}^{(1)}$, $\mathbf{b}^{(1)}$ and \mathbf{W} in Eq.(28) and Eq. (29). For example, when the size of hidden layer is 32, the size of $\mathbf{W}^{(1)}$ is 32 by 13. The corresponding results are shown in Figure 35. It is found that the increase in the size of hidden layer does not stably increase the performance of influence. Therefore, we select the smallest one, which is 32.

Figure 34. The influence of time interval.

Figure 35. Influence of feature size.

5. Conclusions and future work

This study proposes a graph interpretation of microphone array and a noise-propagation graph neural network. Specifically, the bogies that are moving with the train and the distributed microphones are formulated as vertices and their relationships (distance, relative velocity) are considered as edges in a directed bipartite graph. Then, the process of noise propagating and contributing to microphone-received SPL is taken as the message passing between vertices in this graph. Doppler effect is taken into account. After training, the proposed GNN can be used to infer the SWL of each bogie when only the SPLs of microphones are available. The proposed method exhibits the following advantages. Firstly, it naturally encodes the distance between bogies and microphones. Secondly, the signal slices on the time axis are unfolded as subsets of microphone vertices. Thirdly, it allows flexible microphone arrangement. Lastly, for a specific railway line and the same type of train, after model training, it has shown the potential to replace the costly acoustic beamforming system with a flexible microphone array for railway noise source evaluation in regular railway engineering practices.

The data from an in-situ experiment is used to validate the idea and prove its superiority. The following findings can be concluded:

- The proposed GNN model and the distributed array can well infer the SWL in one-third octave frequency bands. In addition, it can also well distinguish different bogies. Specifically, all the MAEs are smaller than 0.8, when the average absolute deviation is around 1~4;
- The proposed GNN model and the distributed array can effectively evaluate the predominant noise sources for a railway acoustic system, with capabilities of both targeting the noisiest regions and inferring the dominant spectrum characteristics with decent accuracy.
- Not considering the Doppler effect only slightly decay the performance of Baseline 1. However, if the training and inference data are not symmetric, the inference result will also exhibit asymmetry;

- When the attenuation effect is not considered, Baseline 2 can still infer the SWL in one-third octave frequency bands. However, the SWLs of different bogies are entangled and cannot be distinguished;
- Although Baseline 3, as a CNN, takes distance and relative velocity as features in the input, it cannot distinguish different bogies. In addition, the fixed input hinders the flexibility of sensor arrangement, which benefits from the graph formulation.

Despite the above advantages and findings, it should be emphasized that the ground truth SWLs for training the GNN are obtained by beamforming. As a result, those issues encountered by beamforming, such as overestimation of wheel contribution (Zhang et al., 2019), will also restrict the performance of GNN. Further advancements (Thompson et al., 2018; Zea et al., 2017) can be taken to provide better labels for GNN. In addition, a complete acoustic colormap can be expected by the proposed algorithm for more generalizable circumstances. It can also be noticed that for different working conditions (train velocity), we formulate different graphs and train different GNNs. In other words, one GNN is applicable to that specific case, which hinders the generalization capability. The authors are undertaking further research on the generalization capability of proposed GNN so that it can be applied to different working conditions (Chen et al., 2020, 2021), by introducing the concept of domain adaptation (Singh et al., 2020; Wilson and Cook, 2020). In recent years, GNNs have also been applied to speech separation (Qin et al., 2020; Tzirakis et al., 2021). Since the problem of evaluating railway noise sources has been reinterpreted in the graph language, i.e., projected into a new research space, the emerging tools in this research space can be better leveraged.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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